

ON ORGANO-ARSENICAL COMPOUNDS. PART II

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Synthesis of *para*-amidinophenylarsenious acid is described.

Although filarial infections are widely distributed in the tropics, no potent and dependable filaricide has yet been discovered. Recently, promising results in the chemotherapy of filariasis have been obtained with some phenylarsenoxide derivatives by Otto and Maren (*Science*, 1947, 106, 105). In course of this investigation, they have found *p*-arsenobenzamide, and specially, *p*-[bis-(carboxy-methylmercapto)-arsino]-benzamide quite active on animal tests. The latter compound has been found to kill all the adults of *D. immitis* in doses which appear to be feasible for man. In view of the recent observations on the pronounced parasitocidal properties of various amidine derivatives (King, Lourie and Yorke, *Lancet*, 1937, 233, 136; Ashley, Barber, Ewins, Newbery and Self, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 103; Kirk and Sati, *Ann. Trop. Med. Parasitol.*, 1940, 34, 82; Adams and Yorke, *ibid.*, 1939, 33, 323; 1940, 34, 174), it has been considered desirable and rational to synthesise *p*-amidinophenylarsenoxide and its derivatives, so that these compounds may be tested for any filaricidal activity.

p-Amidinophenylarsenoxide could not be successfully prepared from *p*-amidinophenylarsonic acid (Linsker and Bogert, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 932) by reduction with sodium bisulphite (compare Doak, Steinman and Eagle, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 3013) of the sodium salt of the arsonic acid in aqueous solution or by reduction of the arsonic acid in dilute sulphuric acid solution with sulphur dioxide in presence of a trace of potassium iodide (D. R. P., 235391).

p-Cyanophenylarsenious acid (I), which has now been prepared by reduction of the aqueous solution of the sodium salt of *p*-cyanophenylarsonic acid (Linsker and Bogert, *loc. cit.*) with sodium bisulphite, has been smoothly converted into *p*-amidinophenylarsenious acid (II), *via* the corresponding imino-ether hydrochloride.

The compound (II) yields a crystalline hydrochloride, which is under pharmacological examination.

EXPERIMENTAL

p-Cyanophenylarsenious Acid (I).—*p*-Cyanophenylarsonic acid (prepared according to the method of Linsker and Bogert, *loc. cit.*, 23 g.) was dissolved in 5% caustic soda solution (80 c. c.) at room temperature. The solution

was diluted with water to 150 c. c. and sodium bisulphite (40 g.) then added with shaking. After filtration to remove any suspended impurity, the solution was allowed to stand at ordinary temperature in a chamber free from acid fumes for 12 days with occasional shaking, when gradually a brownish, crystalline solid was precipitated. The solid was filtered, washed with cold water, triturated with dilute aqueous ammonia, filtered and finally washed thoroughly with water, yield 14 g. It is soluble in cold dilute alkali but insoluble in aqueous ammonia or sodium bicarbonate. It is sparingly soluble in hot water and in alcohol and could not be recrystallised from these solvents. It was, however, purified by solution in dilute alkali and precipitation, under cooling, with hydrochloric acid, and was dried *in vacuo* over fused calcium chloride. It softens at 239° and melts at 253–55° to a viscous liquid. (Found : N, 6.34 ; As, 35.88. $C_7H_8O_2NAs$ requires N, 6.63 ; As, 35.51 per cent).

p-Amidinophenylarsenious Acid (II).—The above compound (I, 15 g.) was finely powdered and suspended in dry ether (45 c.c.) to which absolute alcohol (6 c.c.) was added. Dry hydrochloric acid gas was then passed into this mixture, kept at 0°. Within a few minutes, a clear solution was obtained and on further passing hydrochloric acid gas till saturated, the solution became turbid. The mixture, kept in a well-stoppered flask, was then left in a refrigerator for 10 days with occasional shaking, when the imino-ether hydrochloride separated as a brownish powder, which was filtered off, washed with dry ether and dried in a vacuum desiccator, yield 10g.

The above imino-ether hydrochloride (10g.) was finely powdered and treated with 15% alcoholic ammonia (100 c.c.) and the mixture was heated in a closed vessel at 65° to 70° for 5 hours. After cooling overnight, the almost colorless precipitate was filtered, washed with alcohol and dried in a vacuum desiccator. It was treated with cold, dilute hydrochloric acid and the solution was filtered to remove a minute quantity of suspended impurity and then basified with ammonia. On scratching, the solution gradually yielded a solid which was filtered and washed with cold water till free from any chloride, yield 2.5g. It was crystallised from hot water in colorless plates, which were dried *in vacuo* over fused calcium chloride. It melts to a viscous liquid at 310°. (Found : N, 12.01 ; As, 32.27. $C_7H_9O_2N_2As$ requires N, 12.28 ; As, 32.86 per cent). It is readily soluble in cold, dilute hydrochloric acid and in cold dilute alkali but insoluble in aqueous ammonia or sodium bicarbonate. The *hydrochloride* was obtained as a colorless, crystalline powder by dissolving the compound in requisite quantity of dilute hydrochloric acid and pouring the solution into a large excess of acetone. It does not melt even at 325° and is fairly soluble in cold water.